

OPENSOURCE OBSERVATORY

Understanding the European Open Science Landscape

FACTSHEET FOR FUNDERS & POLICY MAKERS AND RESEARCH PERFORMING ORGANISATIONS

What is it?

<https://osobservatory.openaire.eu>

The **Open Science Observatory** is an OpenAIRE platform showcasing a collection of indicators and visualisations that help interested stakeholders (policy makers and research administrators, among others) better understand the Open Science (OS) landscape in Europe, across and within countries.

Why?

Empowering Leadership and Disruption

The rise of Open Science mandates across countries and scientific fields underscores the growing need for precise, timely tracking of Open Science practices and adoption.

Better understand the European Open Science landscape

- Monitor and enhance Open science policy uptake
- Understand Open Science impact pathways along key dimensions
- See what works and what not, reveal hidden potential
- Identify success stories
- Promote good practices
- Turn data into insights and evidence-based policy-making
- Contribute to the European Open Science Cloud and UNESCO monitoring

How? It's about open data and collaboration

Completeness, inclusion, transparency and replicability

We leverage the **OpenAIRE Graph**, an extensive collection of linked scholarly information from open initiatives around the world, as the foundation for our indicators, encompassing a wide range of research products beyond publications, such as datasets, software, and more. We base our approach on **Open Science Principles** that include open data sources, open APIs and a well documented methodology and further validate data and develop new indicators together with the community to ensure quality and relevance.

Methodological approach in a nutshell

Openness and transparency: Methodological assumptions are openly and clearly presented.

Coverage and accuracy: Based on data from multiple data sources to triangulate to the fullest extent possible, and provide meaningful indicators.

Clarity and replicability: Detailed construction methodology, so that it can be verified and used by the scholarly communication community to create ongoing updates to proposed statistics and indicators.

Readiness and timeliness: Built around well-established open databases and already tested knowledge extraction technologies - natural language processing (NLP) / machine-learning (ML) - using operational workflows in OpenAIRE to warrant timely results.

Trust and robustness: Strive to be reliable, robust, and aligned to other assessment methods so that it can be operationalised, used and reused, in conjunction with them.

Open Access (OA) in Europe

Europe View on OS Observatory

Indicators Themes in the Open Science Observatory

Our **indicators themes** cover various aspects, with multiple indicators and metrics in each theme. They enable the exploration of trends and insights by breaking down the data into dimensions of interest (such as funder, institution, etc.), and support meaningful comparisons across countries and contexts.

We are at your disposal for feedback and suggestions as we shape and expand our indicators to accurately capture the evolving landscape of Open Science.

About OpenAIRE

www.openaire.eu

Shifting scholarly communication towards openness and transparency and facilitate innovative ways to communicate and monitor research.

For more information, please contact: info@openaire.eu

Additional Guidance: www.openaire.eu/guides

Useful Links

Open Science Observatory

<https://osobservatory.openaire.eu/>

Terminology and construction

<https://osobservatory.openaire.eu/methodology#terminology>

Webinar

<https://youtu.be/EilthLvfe14>

Demo

<https://youtu.be/Nl6p5w0QTil>

This factsheet is also available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8147270>